

ANDRZEJ LASON¹ ,

Epuraea (Haptoncus) ocularis FAIRMAIRE, 1849 (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae): the first record in Poland

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¹ ul. Wiejska 4B/85, 15-352 Białystok, Polska, e-mail: haptos@interia.pl, ORCID: 0000-0003-2331-3459

² Department of Natural History, Upper Silesian Museum, pl. Jana III Sobieskiego 2, 41-902 Bytom, Poland

³ e-mail: dobosz@muzeum.bytom.pl ORCID: 0000-0003-4441-5147

⁴ e-mail: czeslaw.gren@vp.pl ORCID: 0000-0001-8500-0525

⁵ e-mail: j.grzywocz@muzeum.bytom.pl ORCID: 0000-0001-6223-816X

Abstract: *Epuraea (Haptoncus) ocularis* FAIRMAIRE, 1849, an invasive species of sap beetle, was found on rotting apples in several localities in Upper Silesia. The species is native to south-eastern Asia and was first recorded in Europe in 1997.

Key words: Coleoptera, Nitidulidae, *Epuraea*, invasive species, Poland.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Epuraea* ERICHSON, 1843 belongs to the subfamily Epuraeinae within the family Nitidulidae. At present, it contains some 300 known species from all over the world; around 150 of them occur in the Palearctic and 27 in Poland.

Originally distributed in south and south-eastern Asia and the western Pacific region, *Epuraea (Haptoncus) ocularis* FAIRMAIRE, 1849 is now regarded as a cosmopolitan species (JELÍNEK & LASON 2018). In Europe, it was officially recorded for the first time in Spain (Canary Islands) in 1997 (JELÍNEK 1997). During the next few years it was also found in Austria, France, Germany, Portugal, Slovenia, Switzerland and Italy; this information was summarized in CPC (JELÍNEK & AUDISIO 2007). Thereafter, it was recorded in Albania (DENUX & ZAGATTI 2010), Czech Republic (VÁVRA *et al.* 2016), Malta (MIFSUD & AUDISIO 2008), Russia (TSINKEVICH & SOLODOVNIKOV 2014, BIBIN 2017) and Hungary (MERKL & SZALÓKI 2020).

E. ocularis was discovered in a few localities in Upper Silesia (S Poland). Apart from the single specimen from Ligota Dolna that was sifted from rotting grain, all the others were captured in rotting apples lying at the foot of apple trees (Fig. 2), deliberately deployed in bait traps on the ground (Fig. 3), or hung from branches at various distances from gardens.

Upper Silesia:

Bytom-Rozbark [CA57], 23.10.2023 – 1 ex., 31.10.2023 – 2 exx., leg. J. Grzywocz;

Bytom-Szombierki [CA47], 23.10.2023 – 2 exx., leg. J. Grzywocz;

Ligota Dolna [BA99], 14.10.2023, 1 ex., leg. J. Grzywocz;

Ruda Śląska-Kochłowice [CA56], 14.07.2022 – 1 ex.; 17-21.08.2023 – 8 exx., leg. Cz. Greń;

Ruda Śląska-Wirek [CA47], 21.09.2023 – 1 ex., 28.09.2023 – 2 exx., 23.10.2023 – 40 exx., 6.11.2023 – 5 exx., leg. J. Grzywocz;

Widów [CA18], 11.10.2023 – 9 exx., leg. R. Dobosz and J. Grzywocz; 12.10.2023 – 23 exx., leg. R. Dobosz.

The voucher specimens are deposited in the collections of the authors and the Upper Silesian Museum, Bytom (USMB).

DISCUSSION

In recent years, several nitidulid beetle species regarded as invasive have been recorded in Poland. One of them is *Glischrochilus grandis* TOURNIER, 1872, first discovered in the Białowieża Forest and the Bieszczady Mts. in 2015 (LASON & HOLLY 2015), and later at a few localities in the Podlasie region (MOKRZYCKI *et al.* 2022, LASON 2023) and in the Eastern Beskid Mts. (TWARDY 2018). As this is a species colonizing woodland biotopes, its spread is necessarily slow. The situation with *Stelidota geminata* (SAY, 1825) is different, occurring as it does in both woodland and synanthropic biotopes. First found in Poland in 2018 (KRÓLIK 2019), it has become an abundant and common species in the south of the country (GRZYWOCZ & GREŃ 2022, also unpubl. data). Another newly discovered beetle is *Caplothorax lugubris* (MURRAY, 1864). Though considered a pest of maize crops and various fruit, it was found in Poland in a woodland biotope (LASON & RUTA 2023).

E. ocularis is thus one more invasive species in the Polish fauna. In most localities in Europe, and also at the new ones in Poland, it has been found above all together with *S. geminata*. The larvae of *E. ocularis* develop in rotting fruit, and also in decomposing herbaceous plants and the sporocarps of fungi. Pupation takes place in the soil. The adults inhabit the same substrates, but also visit flowers and are attracted by artificial sources of light (TSINKEVICH & SOLODOVNIKOV 2014).

Epuraea ocularis is a very characteristically coloured species (Fig. 1), even the discoloured or teneral specimens can be easily distinguished from all our *Epuraea* according to the acutely pointed temples behind eyes.

REFERENCES

- BIBIN A.R. 2017. Invasive sap beetles *Epuraea ocularis* and *Stelidota geminata* (Coleoptera, Nitidulidae) in the Russian Black Sea region. *Russian Journal of Biological Invasions* 8: 301–302.
- DENUX O., ZAGATTI P. 2010. Coleoptera families other than Cerambycidae, Curculionidae sensu lato, Chrysomelidae sensu lato and Coccinellidae. Chapter 8.5, pp. 315–406, In: ROQUES A., KENIS M., LEES D., LOPEZ-VAAMONDE C., RABITSCH W., RASPLUS J.-Y., ROY D. (Eds), Alien terrestrial arthropods of Europe. *Biorisk* 4.
- GRZYWOCZ J., GREŃ C. 2022. Materiały do poznania koleopterofauny (Insecta: Coleoptera) Śląska: cz. 1. *Acta entomologica silesiana* 30(017): 1–13 [online]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7281616>.
- JELÍNEK J. 1997. Revision of the genus *Epuraea* Er. from Africa with remarks to related genera (Col., Nitidulidae). *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* 39: 345–397.
- JELÍNEK J., AUDISIO P. 2007. Nitidulidae, pp. 459–491, In: LÖBL I., SMETANA A. (Eds.), Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, Vol. 4. Stenstrup, Apollo Books.
- JELÍNEK J., LASON A. 2018. New species of *Epuraea* (*Haptoncus*) from New Caledonia (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae, Epuraeinae). *Annals of Upper Silesian Museum, Entomology* 26(008): 1–11 [online]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1200108>.
- KRÓLIK R. 2019. Dane o występowaniu w Polsce kilku nowych i niedawno odkrytych gatunków chrząszczy (Coleoptera). *Acta entomologica silesiana* 27(011): 1–5 [online]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3249864>.

- LASOŃ A. 2023. *Glischrochilus tremulae* CLAYHILLS, AUDISIO & CLINE, 2016 nowy gatunek dla fauny Polski oraz podsumowanie stanu wiedzy o rozmieszczeniu na Podlasiu chrząszczy z rodzin Kateretidae i Nitidulidae (Coleoptera). *Rocznik Muzeum Górnośląskiego w Bytomiu, Przyroda* 29(017): 1–25 [online]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117843>.
- LASOŃ A., HOLLY M. 2015. *Glischrochilus grandis* TOURNIER, 1872 – nowy gatunek chrząszcza dla fauny Polski oraz nowe dane o rozszedzeniu przedstawicieli rodzaju *Glischrochilus* REITTER, 1873 (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae: Cryptarchinae). *Acta entomologica silesiana* 31: 1–4.
- LASOŃ A., RUTA R. 2023. Pierwsze stwierdzenie *Caplothorax lugubris* (MURRAY, 1864) (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae) w Polsce. *Acta entomologica silesiana* 31(013): 1–4 [online]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8333996>.
- MERKL O., SZALÓKI D. 2020. Four new alien beetle species in Hungary (Coleoptera). *Folia Entomologica Hungarica* 81: 33–41.
- MIFSUD D., AUDISIO P. 2008. The Kateretidae and Nitidulidae of the Maltese Archipelago (Coleoptera). *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Malta* 1: 15–37.
- MOKRZYCKI T., BOHDAN A., KOWAL B., LASOŃ A., SZTABKOWSKA I. 2022. Rzadkie i nowe gatunki chrząszczy (Coleoptera) dla Puszczy Białowieskiej. *Wiadomości entomologiczne* 41(3), online 16A: 20–25.
- TSINKEVICH V.A. & SOLODOVNIKOV I.A. 2014. First record of sap beetles *Epuraea ocularis* and *Stelidota geminata* (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae) from Caucasus. *Zoosystematica Rossica* 23(1): 118–121.
- TWARDY D. 2018. Nowe stwierdzenie *Glischrochilus (Librodor) grandis* (TOURNIER, 1872) (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae: Cryptarchinae) w Polsce. *Wiadomości entomologiczne* 37(2): 122–123.
- VÁVRA J.CH., PRŮDEK P., HAUCK D., ČÍZEK L. 2016: Faunistic Records from the Czech Republic – 403. Coleoptera: Ptinidae, Nitidulidae, Monotomidae. *Klapalekiana* 52: 99–101.

Fig. 1. *Epuraea ocularis* – specimen from Ruda Śląska-Kochłowice (photo A. Lasoń).

Fig. 2. The locality *Epuraea ocularis* in the old orchard in Widów (photo R. Dobosz).

Fig. 3. Fruit trap in Ruda Śląska-Wirek (photo J. Grzywocz).

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